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Alkbh3 functions with Nupr1 in a n1-methyladenosine dependent manner.

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We measured total in conjunction with N1-methyladenosine marks in human cells lacking Alkbh3 to understand function of the m1A mark in transcriptional biology and the immune system. We demonstrate here interaction of Alkbh3 with *Nupr1*.

Citations

1. Liu, J., Song, X., Kuang, F., Zhang, Q., Xie, Y., Kang, R., Kroemer, G. and Tang, D., 2021. NUPR1 is a critical repressor of ferroptosis. Nature communications, 12(1), p.647.

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